

Does the Kaniadakis Distribution Contain More Information than the Constraints Sum over i eⁱ p(e_i) = E and Sum over i p(e_i) = 1?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. July 5, 2025

In (1), we argued that one may create an entropy (or lack of information function) which only contains the information of the two constraints: Sum over i f(e_i) p(e_i) = F and Sum over i p(e_i) = 1. (In the Tsallis case, Sum over i p(e_i)^q f(e_i) = F holds.)

We showed this entropy: $G = \sum_i A(p(e_i)) B(p(e_i)) \rightarrow dG=0$ such that the first derivative term maps to the differential of one constraint and the other, to the second. This approach was shown to apply to the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis cases. This is an interesting result, because two distributions which appear in nature only contain the information of these two constraints and nothing else.

We then noted that the Kaniadakis case was a little more complicated. It is strongly based on the information of Sum over i f(e_i) p(e_i) = F, but not on Sum over i p(e_i) = 1. We then suggested that more information than the second constraint Sum over i p(e_i)=1 is required to describe the Kaniadakis case, which also appears in nature. Here we try to explain why this extra information is needed.

Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis Cases

Given two constraints: Sum over i f(e_i) p(e_i) = F ((1a)) and Sum over i p(e_i) = 1 ((1b)) (in the Tsallis case, one has Sum over i f(e_i) p(e_i)^q = F ((1c))), one may immediately write the differentials:

$$\sum_i f(e_i) dp(e_i) = 0 \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{Tsallis case: } \sum_i f(e_i) p(e_i)^{q-1} dp(e_i) = 0 \quad ((2b))$$

$$\text{and } \sum_i dp(e_i) = 0 \quad ((2c))$$

Mathematically, the above conditions may be used to create a function which only contains the information of these constraints and so when extremized, reproduces ((2a))/((2 b)) and ((2c)). In particular, because there are two constraints and they are in the form of sum over p(e_i), one has:

$$G = \sum_i A(p(e_i)) B(p(e_i)) \rightarrow dG=0 = \sum_i dA/dp(e_i) dp(e_i) B + \sum_i A dB/dp(e_i) dp(e_i) \quad ((3))$$

$$\text{Mapping: } dA/dp(e_i) dp(e_i) = dp(e_i) \text{ and } B= f(e_i) \text{ and } A dB/dp(e_i) = 1 \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{For the Maxwell -Boltzmann case, one finds that: } A= p(e_i), \quad p(e_i) d/dp(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) = 1 \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{For the Tsallis case: } A = p(e_i)^q \text{ so } p(e_i)^q dB/dp(e_i) = 1 \text{ and:}$$

$$B = \{1 + (1-q) p(e_i) \text{ power } (1-q)\} / (1-q) \text{ so that } q \rightarrow 1 \text{ yields } B = \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((6))$$

Given that $B(p(e_i)) = -1/T f(e_i)$, one may find both the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis distributions, given their respective B forms.

This result is interesting because it says that there exists a function:

$G = \text{Sum over } i \ A(p(e_i))B(p(e_i))$ which only contains the information of the two constraints and no other information. When G is maximized, one obtains the two distributions which appear in nature.

It seems, however, that a third distribution, the Kaniadakis one (in various forms i.e. exp-k and Gaussian -k depending on the form of $f(e_i)$) also exists and does not fully follow the recipe given above. It does, however, partially follow this recipe. We suggest then that the Kaniadakis distribution is associated with a priori extra information than that contained in the two usual constraints ((1a)), ((1b)).

The Kaniadakis Case

The Kaniadakis case is based on the idea that the constraint $\text{Sum over } i \ f(e_i) p(e_i) = F$ is important, just as in the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis cases. In fact, the Kaniadakis approach follows the form:

$$G = \text{Sum over } i \ A(p(e_i)) B(p(e_i)) \text{ with } dG=0 \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{It then sets: } A(p(e_i)) = p(e_i) \text{ and } B(p(e_i)) = -1/T f(e_i) \quad ((8))$$

At this point, it is identical with the Maxwell-Boltzmann approach. The Kaniadakis approach, however, a priori is linked with power law form $p(e_i) \text{ power } k$ which must be different from the Tsallis case. The Kaniadakis approach uses $\text{Sum over } i \ p(e_i) f(e_i)$ and not $\text{Sum over } i \ p(e_i) \text{ power } q f(e_i)$ a priori. It, however, does something more drastic which makes it impossible to have this distribution only depend on the information of the two constraints ((1a)) and ((1b)).

If one revisits the MB form:

$$p(e_i) dB/dp(e_i) = 1 \quad ((9))$$

$$\text{The Tsallis form is: } p(e_i) \text{ power } q \ dB/dp(e_i) = 1 \quad ((10))$$

Thus, if $p(e_i)$ is assumed to be a falling function with e_i , then $dB/dp(e_i)$ is an increasing function of e_i to cancel with $p(e_i)$ or $p(e_i) \text{ power } q$. It cannot be a combined increasing or decreasing function in e_i . We see that $B(p(e_i))$ is important because of its link to the constraint ((1a)).

The Kaniadakis approach assumes that one may create a $dB/dp(e_i)$ as a sum of both an increasing and decreasing function of e_i . In other words, one may combine positive and negative powers of $p(e_i)$ meaning that the slope $dB/dp(e_i)$ in ((9)) and ((10)) cannot possibly

cancel with $p(e_i)$ or $p(e_i)$ power single number. This also means that $B(p(e_i))$ contains such a combination. This is extra a priori information beyond ((1a)) and ((1b)), we argue.

As a result, ((9)) and ((10)), which map to the constraint $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ cannot be used for the Kaniadakis case because there must be some additional a priori information present. We argue that this a priori information is present because one wishes to have B be a function of $p(e_i)$ power k and $p(e_i)$ power $-k$ meaning that its derivative $dB/dp(e_i)$ will also be mixed. In particular,

$$B(p(e)) = 1/(2k) \{ p(e_i)^k - p(e_i)^{-k} \} \quad ((11))$$

$$\text{Then: } p \, dB/dp(e_i) = \frac{1}{2} \{ p(e_i)^k + p(e_i)^{-k} \} \quad ((12))$$

If one wishes to use the maximization approach listed above, then:

$$\sum_i dp(e_i) p \, dB/dp(e_i) = 0 \quad ((13))$$

((13)), however, represents an extra piece of information beyond the two constraints ((1a)) and ((1b)) as stated above. Thus, physically the Kaniadakis distribution seems to be quite different from the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis ones. It deliberately mixes $p(e_i)$ power k with $p(e_i)$ power $-k$ and this seems to be linked to extra physical information not contained in the constraints ((1a)) and ((1b)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Tsallis scenarios are based on only the information of the constraints $\sum_i p(e_i) f(e_i) = F$ (or $\sum_i p(e_i)^q f(e_i)$ in the Tsallis case) and $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$. The key idea is to create an entropy or information function $G = \sum_i A(p(e_i)) B(p(e_i))$ with $dG=0$ such that the two derivative terms map to differentials of the two constraints because there is no extra information present. This implies that $A(p(e_i)) = p(e_i)$ or $p(e_i)^q$ in the Tsallis case and $B(p(e_i)) = -1/T f(e_i)$. A key requirement is then that: $p(e_i) dB/dp(e_i) = 1$ (or $p(e_i)^q dB/dp(e_i) = 1$ in the Tsallis case). $dB/dp(e_i)$ must represent a function which either rises or drops with e_i to cancel with $p(e_i)$ or $p(e_i)^q$. It cannot be a combination.

The Kaniadakis case retains much of the same formalism listed above, but insists on a mixed $p(e_i)$ power k and $p(e_i)$ power $-k$ in the form of B . This means that the slope $dB/dp(e_i)$ will also be mixed and so cannot combine with $p(e_i)$ to form 1. In other words, there is more information (physical information) than $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$. One needs the extra condition: $\sum_i dp(e_i) \{p(e_i)^k + p(e_i)^{-k}\} = 0$ and this is an extra piece of information. Thus, the Kaniadakis distribution, which appears in nature, is one in which more information than simply the two usual constraints ((1a)) and ((1b)) exist, we argue.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. An Interpretation of Maxwell-Boltzmann, Tsallis Entropy (preprint, zenodo, 2025)